

Petit Plasmid: A Small, Versatile Antibiotic-Free Multi-Application DNA Vector Driving Biotech Innovation

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Introduction

DNA plasmids find wide-ranging applications in diverse fields of research, including studies related to inflammatory and autoimmune diseases [1], infectious diseases [2], therapeutic cancer vaccines [3,4], gene therapy [5,6], cell therapy [6–8], production of recombinant and therapeutic proteins [9,10], and viral vector production [11–13].

The utilization of antibiotic resistance genes as selectable markers is discouraged due to the potential uptake of the plasmid by endogenous bacterial flora. This could lead to the emergence and dissemination of antibiotic-resistant microbes. The presence of prokaryotic sequences and CpG dinucleotides should be minimized in clinical applications. While these elements are useful for the plasmid's maintenance within bacterial hosts, they can trigger adverse immune reactions when introduced into mammalian cells [14].

To satisfy regulatory agencies recommendations and develop safer and more effective products, a variety of antibiotic-free plasmids and their corresponding host strains were developed [15–22].

Herein, I disclose novel antibiotic resistance gene-free DNA plasmids and provide comprehensive details about the generation of exemplary strains capable of supporting their maintenance and replication.

Green et al. introduced regulators called "Toehold Switches," which involve an RNA hairpin structure that sequesters both the Ribosome Binding Site (RBS) and a Start codon [23]. In the presence of a trigger RNA, which interacts with a complementary region located at the 5' region of the hairpin, the RBS is exposed, enabling ribosomes to initiate translation of the downstream sequence. Remarkably, a single pair of switch-trigger RNA led to a substantial average fold-activation exceeding 400.

Chappell et al. presented the concept of "small transcription activating RNAs" (STARs), designed to bind to a complementary region located upstream of a terminator or its 5' portion. This interaction prevents the formation of a terminating hairpin, thereby allowing the transcription of a downstream gene [24]. Notably, one specific pair of STAR-RNA target (AD1 A5/S5) exhibited a striking level of regulation, achieving a 94-fold activation. Remarkable levels of gene activation, reaching up to 9000-fold, were attained through the utilization of a computationally-optimized combination of STAR : hairpin RNA and a mutant green fluorescent protein with reduced half-life [25].

Westbrook et al. disclosed a "dual transcription-translation activator" having a near-background basal activity in the un-induced state yet displaying an average activation level of 923-fold upon the presence of small transcription activating RNAs (STARs) [26]. The STAR-inducible switch is called a "dual control activator" and comprises a terminator sequence encompassing a concealed ribosome binding site (RBS), a poly-A tail, and a downstream Start codon. When STARs are absent, a terminating hairpin structure forms, leading to transcription termination. The RBS is concealed within the hairpin, effectively preventing undesired translation initiation of the transcript. When present, STARs bind a complementary region of the terminator, preventing the formation of a terminating hairpin and subsequently exposing the RBS. This orchestrated interplay facilitates both transcription and translation of the downstream coding sequence.

By fusing designed toehold sequences with either artificial or natural terminator sequences, Hong et al. produced novel "switchable transcription terminators" (SWTs) [27]. Specific trigger RNAs hybridize with the toehold region as well as a portion of the terminator, effectively hindering the formation of a terminating hairpin, and enabling the uninterrupted elongation of transcription. It is noteworthy that a

SWT derived from T500 terminator displayed minimal leakage in the un-induced state and showcased an outstanding fold-activation of up to 879 upon induction.

When a bacterial strain is knocked-out for an important gene G, it can become auxotrophic with respect to a substrate S [28]. For example, G can be the gene *argA*, *hisB*, *ilvA*, *leuB*, *lysA*, *metA*, *pheA*, *proA*, *thrC*, *trpC*, or *tyrA*, while S corresponds to the amino acid L-arginine, L-Histidine, L-Isoleucine, L-Leucine, L-Lysine, L-Methionine, L-Phenylalanine, L-Proline, L-Threonine, L-Tryptophan, or tyrosine, respectively [28]. To achieve regulated expression in the presence of small transcription activating RNAs (STARs), a dual transcription-translation activator sequence could be inserted upstream of the important gene G. The resultant DNA construct can then be integrated into the genome of a bacterial strain or its auxotrophic variants, leading to the generation of engineered conditionally-auxotrophic strains.

The antibiotic marker-free plasmids disclosed herein are called “Petit Plasmids” and comprise at least a STAR cassette and an origin of replication sequence. STAR cassette comprises a prokaryotic promoter, a STAR-encoding gene, and a prokaryotic terminator—all required for producing STAR transcripts. The origin of replication sequence (*ori*) is required for plasmid maintenance within a bacterial host. Exemplary origin of replication sequences include the minimal R6Ky, which necessitates the in-trans expression of the π protein for plasmid replication [29–31], and *colE2-P9*, which relies on the *parA* for plasmid replication [32–34]. When this plasmid is introduced in an engineered conditionally-auxotrophic strain of the present disclosure, STARs are produced, the important gene G is unexpressed, and the substrate S becomes optional for growth. In the absence of the plasmid and without supplementing the culture medium with S, bacterial growth will either be inhibited or the cells will die.

Design

Petit Plasmid comprises a STAR cassette, serving as a selectable marker, and an origin of replication sequence, necessary for the plasmid’s maintenance and replication within a suitable bacterial host. A STAR cassette comprises a promoter, a STAR-encoding sequence, and a terminator. We will henceforth refer to the transcripts produced from the STAR cassette as “activating RNAs”. They bind a complementary region of an RNA sequence, hereafter referred to as an “RNA switch”. The interaction of an activating RNA with a complementary region of an RNA switch results in transcription elongation that subsequently leads to the translation of the nascent protein-encoding RNA sequence.

Pairs of “activating RNA” and “RNA switch” for use in the present disclosure can be sourced from Ref [23–27], patents WO2015161060A1 and WO2014074648A2.

Production of activating RNAs can be tuned by varying the strength of the promoter, which can be selected from various sources such as Chris Anderson’s collection of promoters, iGEM’s BIOFAB collection, or those disclosed in Ref [35,36]. Without being bound to a particular theory or mechanism, a very weak promoter will lead to the production of a small amount of activating RNA, thus favoring the growth of bacteria bearing multiple copies of Petit Plasmids. The promoter can further comprise an insulator in its 5’ terminal to minimize the effects of transcriptional interference caused by a cryptic promoter sequence located upstream of the STAR cassette (for detail, see Ref [37]).

A chromosomally integrated DNA cassette known as “Activating RNA-Inducible Gene of Interest” (ARIGoI), illustrated in Figure 1, encodes the RNA switch and the protein-encoding RNA sequence. Its antibiotic resistance and counter-selectable marker cassettes (*SacB*) can be removed from the sequence by using Flp

recombinase-mediated excision. The result is illustrated in Figure 2. The effects of the presence or absence of “activating RNAs” as well as supplementing or omitting the “substrate S” on bacterial cells growth are summarized in Figure 3. For streamlining integration processes, additional cassettes, such as those encoding π protein or *parA* protein (replication gene), can be inserted into ARIGol. The construct is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 1: Components of “Activating RNA-Inducible Gene of Interest” (ARIGol).

Figure 2: Chromosomally-integrated “Activating RNA-Inducible Gene of Interest” (ARIGol) after *Flp*-mediated excision of the antibiotic resistance and *SacB* cassettes.

The promoter (promoter 1) that drives π or *parA* expression can be of varying strength. Their Ribosome binding site’s sequence can be modified in order to modulate plasmid copy number (for detail, see Ref [34]). Further strategies for varying plasmid copy numbers are disclosed in the prior art [38,39].

The Gene of Interest (GoI) of an ARIGol encodes for an “important polypeptide”, required for synthesizing an essential substrate S. The GoI might correspond to *Escherichia coli*’s *argA*, *hisB*, *ilvA*, *leuB*, *lysA*, *metaA*, *proA*, *pheA*, *thrC*, *trpC*, or *tyrA*, where S corresponds to the amino acid L-arginine, L-Histidine, L-Isoleucine, L-Leucine, L-Lysine, L-Methionine, L-Proline, L-Phenylalanine, L-Threonine, L-Tryptophan, or tyrosine, respectively. Its promoter (promoter 2) is preferably devoid of a Ribosome binding site and can be selected from a collection of promoters of varying strength, such as Chris Anderson’s promoters, iGEM’s BIOFAB collection, or those disclosed in Ref [35,36].

The “important polypeptide” can comprise a degron sequence in its C-terminal. Exemplary degron sequences are disclosed in Table 1 of Ref [40]. An example of a popular degron is *ssrA* tag (AANDENYALAA) [41]. Without being bound to a particular theory or mechanism, lowering the polypeptide’s half-life has the effect of improving the ON/OFF ratio (fold activation) of the system. This, in turn, leads to improved inhibition and/or elimination of bacteria lacking Petit Plasmids during selection.

A bacterial strain that supports the maintenance and replication of Petit Plasmids can be generated by first knocking-out a Gol using methods well known in the art [28,42,43], converting the cells into an auxotrophic strain for a substrate S, and then chromosomally integrating ARIGol using methods well known in the art [44–46]. ARIGol can comprise a replication cassette that encodes replication proteins required for the maintenance and replication of plasmids harboring an origin of replication, such as the minimal R6Ky or the minimal colE2-P9. Alternatively, the replication cassette can be inserted during a distinct integration step. The resulting engineered conditionally-auxotrophic strain can be propagated in a medium supplemented with the substrate S or preserved by preparing glycerol stocks, which are stored at -80°C.

Figure 3: Effects of the presence or absence of “activating RNAs” and “substrate S” on bacterial growth.

Figure 4: “Activating RNA-Inducible Gene of Interest” (ARIGol) with an upstream replication cassette.

Following bacterial transformation with Petit Plasmids, transformants are selected by culturing cells in a chemically-defined agar plates or media that lacks the substrate S. Seed cultures can be started by streaking colonies on minimal agar plates lacking the substrate S. After incubation at 30-37°C for 11-18h, well-isolated and colony PCR-verified colonies are inoculated in media lacking the substrate S to provide 0.01-1% inoculums for use in laboratory-scale or large-scale fermentation. Media used for culture or fermentation should lack the substrate S, or should not be supplemented with the substrate S if it was initially present. Plasmids are extracted and purified using commercially-available kits or methods well known in the art [47].

Implementation

Lambda red recombineering is a useful tool for inserting a high molecular weight DNA sequence into specific target sites within a bacterial chromosome [44]. Here, I take advantage of this tool to simultaneously knock-out the *lysA* gene of *E. coli* and insert a cassette (referred to as *pir_induc_lysA* or *parA_induc_lysA*) comprising a replication cassette encoding a replication protein, a dual transcription-translation activator-controllable *lysA* gene, and an antibiotic resistance cassette. The replication protein can either be a π protein for the maintenance of a circular DNA plasmid bearing a minimal R6K γ origin of replication or a *repA* protein for the maintenance of a circular DNA plasmid bearing a minimal *colE2-P9* origin of replication. The antibiotic resistance cassette is removed by transforming the strain with a plasmid expressing an F₁ recombinase [48].

DNA sequences and Plasmids

pR6K γ MCS (pR6K γ _MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid R6K γ noPT (PP_R6K γ _noPT_MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid R6K γ MCS (PP_R6K γ _MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid R6K γ Tol2 (PP_R6K γ _Tol2_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon.

Petit plasmid R6K γ ePB (PP_R6K γ _ePB_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Piggybac transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Piggybac transposon.

Petit plasmid R6K γ SB (PP_R6K γ _SB_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Sleeping Beauty transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Sleeping Beauty transposon.

Plasmid pR6K γ _eGFP, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_noPT, PP_R6K γ _eGFP, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_Tol2, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_ePB, and PP_R6K γ _eGFP_SB are circular DNA sequences obtained by cloning an enhanced Green Fluorescent Protein (eGFP) cassette into the MCS of pR6K γ _MCS, PP_R6K γ _noPT_MCS, PP_R6K γ _MCS, PP_R6K γ _Tol2_MCS, PP_R6K γ _ePB_MCS, and PP_R6K γ _SB_MCS, respectively. The sequence of eGFP cassette is in Supplementary Table S2.

pR6K γ _Tol2_MCS (a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an R6K γ origin of replication, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon.

pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry is a circular DNA sequence obtained by cloning a DsRed Fluorescent Protein (mCherry) cassette (sequence in Supplementary Table S2) into the MCS of pR6Ky_Tol2_MCS. The mCherry cassette comprises: a CMV promoter, a *Homo sapiens* codon-optimized DsRed Fluorescent Protein gene, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR) cassette, and a polyadenylation sequence. The STAR cassette comprises: a promoter, a sequence encoding a small transcription activating RNA, and a terminator.

pcolE2-P9 MCS (pcolE2-P9_MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid colE2-P9 noPT (PP_colE2-P9_noPT_MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid colE2-P9 MCS (PP_colE2-P9_MCS, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, and a multiple cloning site (MCS).

Petit plasmid colE2-P9 Tol2 (PP_colE2-P9_Tol2_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon.

Petit plasmid colE2-P9 ePB (PP_colE2-P9_ePB_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Piggybac transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Piggybac transposon.

Petit plasmid colE2-P9 SB (PP_colE2-P9_SB_MCS, a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: a colE2-P9 origin of replication, a promoter, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR), a terminator, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Sleeping Beauty transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Sleeping Beauty transposon.

Plasmid pcolE2-P9_eGFP, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_noPT, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_Tol2, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_ePB, and PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_SB are circular DNA sequences obtained by cloning an enhanced Green Fluorescent Protein (eGFP) cassette into the MCS of pcolE2-P9_MCS, PP_colE2-P9_noPT_MCS, PP_colE2-P9_MCS, PP_colE2-P9_Tol2_MCS, PP_colE2-P9_ePB_MCS, and PP_colE2-P9_SB_MCS, respectively. The sequence of eGFP cassette is in Supplementary Table S2.

pcolE2-P9_Tol2_MCS (a transposon plasmid, sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a circular DNA sequence comprising: an colE2-P9 origin of replication, a truncated 5' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon, a multiple cloning site (MCS), and a truncated 3' flanking region of a Tol2 transposon.

pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry is a circular DNA sequence obtained by cloning a DsRed Fluorescent Protein (mCherry) cassette (sequence in Supplementary Table S2) into the MCS of pcolE2-P9_Tol2_MCS. The mCherry cassette comprises: a CMV promoter, a *Homo sapiens* codon-optimized DsRed Fluorescent Protein gene, a small transcription activating RNA (STAR) cassette, and a polyadenylation sequence. The

STAR cassette comprises: a promoter, a sequence encoding a small transcription activating RNA, and a terminator.

The cassette *parA_induc_lysA* (sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a linear DNA sequence comprising: a 79-nt left homologous arm taken from the 5' region of *lysA* gene, a terminator sequence to attenuate the transcriptional interference caused by the upstream *lysA* promoter, a constitutive promoter, a sequence encoding *parA* protein, a terminator, a constitutive promoter, a dual transcription-translation activator sequence, a sequence encoding *E. coli* diaminopimelate decarboxylase (*lysA*), a wild-type Flp recombinase binding site (*Frt*), a terminator, a constitutive promoter, a sequence encoding aminoglycoside phosphotransferase (*kanR*), a ribosome binding site, a sequence encoding *B. subtilis* Levansucrase (*sacB*), a wild-type Flp recombinase binding site, a bidirectional terminator, and an 80-nt right homologous arm taken from the 3' region of *lysA* gene.

The cassette *pir_induc_lysA* (sequence in Supplementary Table S2) is a linear DNA sequence comprising: a 79-nt left homologous arm taken from the 5' region of *lysA* gene, a terminator sequence to attenuate the transcriptional interference caused by the upstream *lysA* promoter, a constitutive promoter, a sequence encoding π protein, a terminator, a constitutive promoter, a dual transcription-translation activator sequence, a sequence encoding *E. coli* diaminopimelate decarboxylase (*lysA*), a wild-type Flp recombinase binding site (*Frt*), a terminator, a constitutive promoter, a sequence encoding aminoglycoside phosphotransferase (*kanR*), a ribosome binding site, a sequence encoding *B. subtilis* Levansucrase (*sacB*), a wild-type Flp recombinase binding site, a bidirectional terminator, and an 80-nt right homologous arm taken from the 3' region of *lysA* gene.

parA_induc_lysA and *pir_induc_lysA* will serve for the generation of engineered auxotrophic strains that support the maintenance and replication of circular DNA plasmids bearing a minimal *colE2-P9* and *R6Ky* origin of replication, respectively.

pir_induc_lysA or *parA_induc_lysA* can be synthesized de-novo in full or in fragments, which are combined together using cloning kits such as Master Mix Gibson assembly[®]. *SacB* is used for negative selection and is optional. Its coding sequence can be removed from the construct to reduce its size. *KanR* is used for positive selection in the presence of the antibiotic Kanamycin. *KanR* and *SacB* are excised from the bacterial chromosome by transforming the cell with a plasmid expressing Flp recombinases.

The cassette *pir_induc_lysA* or *parA_induc_lysA* is PCR-amplified with the following primers (designed from the sequence NZ_JANCYZ010000002, genbank):

- Forward: 5'-GCACTTATCTGGAGTTTGTATGCCACATTC-3',
- And Reverse: 5'- GTCATCATGCAACCAGCGACTAACC -3'.

PCR products are run on agarose gel, then the band of the correct size is cut-out and processed using an appropriate gel extraction kit by following instructor's manual.

Strain engineering

Some exemplary *Escherichia coli* strains suitable for the generation of engineered auxotrophic strains are available in Table 1. If the strain is commercially-available, vendor's instructions should be followed carefully. For example, Stbl3[®] strains are already chemically competent and shouldn't be used for electroporation. After the completion of a given step, glycerol stocks of any generated strains can be prepared and then stored at the appropriate temperature (-80°C).

Here, I disclose a method of obtaining engineered L-lysine auxotrophic strains that can support the maintenance and replication of plasmids bearing an R6K γ origin of replication. Adapting this method to generate engineered L-lysine auxotrophic strains that can support the maintenance and replication of plasmids bearing a colE2-P9 origin of replication is straightforward and consists of replacing *pir_induc_lysA* with *parA_induc_lysA* in the protocols.

The amounts of antibiotics added to culture media are: kanamycin (50 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), ampicillin (100 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), and chloramphenicol (34 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$).

Table 1: *Escherichia coli* strains

Name	Genotype
Stbl2[®]	F- endA1 <i>glnV44 thi1 recA1 gyrA96 relA1</i> $\Delta(\text{lac-proAB})$ <i>mcrA</i> $\Delta(\text{mcrBC-hsdRMS-mrr})$ λ -
Stbl3[®]	F-mcrB <i>mrr hsdS20 (rB-, mB-)</i> <i>recA13 supE44 ara14 galK2 lacY1 proA2 rpsL20 (StrR) xyl5</i> λ - <i>leu mtl1</i>
DH5α	F- ϕ 80dlac Δ M15 $\Delta(\text{lacZYA-argF})$ U169 <i>endA1 recA1 hsdR17 (rK- mK+)</i> <i>deoR thi1 phoA supE44</i> λ - <i>gyrA96 relA1</i>
DH10B	F-mcrA $\Delta(\text{mrr-hsdRMS-mcrBC})$ ϕ 80dlac Δ M15 $\Delta(\text{lacX74})$ <i>endA1 recA1 deoR</i> $\Delta(\text{ara, leu})$ 7,697 <i>araD139 galU galK nupG rpsL</i> λ -
Top10	F-mcrA $\Delta(\text{mrr-hsdRMS-mcrBC})$ ϕ 80lac Δ M15 $\Delta(\text{lacX74})$ <i>recA1 araD139</i> $\Delta(\text{ara-leu})$ 7,697 <i>galU galK rpsL (StrR) endA1 nupG</i>

pKD46 is a temperature-sensitive plasmid that encodes an arabinose-inducible lambda red recombination system. It is transfected into a selected strain by chemical transformation or electroporation. Successful recombinants are selected on plates with ampicillin at a temperature between 30-32 °C. After overnight growth, 5-20 colonies are inoculated into LB (Luria Bertani) medium with ampicillin and screened by colony PCR to identify transformants harboring the pKD46-encoded lambda red recombination system. Media containing positive colonies are grown to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.2 at 30°C. 1% (w/v) of L-arabinose is added to the media, and the culture is grown at 30°C until the OD₆₀₀ reaches 0.4-0.6. Before performing electroporation, the cells should be washed with ice-cold deionized water 2-3 times by repeated pelleting (by centrifugation) and resuspension. After the last pelleting, cells are resuspended in 10% glycerol.

The gel-purified linear *pir_induc_lysA* is electroporated or chemically transformed into the cells. Use between 30-150 μl of the cell culture and add a volume containing 2-5 μl of *pir_induc_lysA* DNA. After transformation, immediately pour the suspension into 1-2 mL of LB medium (Luria Bertani broth contains L-lysine) and allow the cells to recover by incubating at 37°C for 1 hour. Spread the bacterial culture on LB plates with kanamycin and incubate overnight at 37°C. Pick 5-20 colonies, inoculate into LB (Luria Bertani) medium with kanamycin, and screen by colony PCR to identify and confirm transformants harboring the chromosomally integrated *pir_induc_lysA*. The following primers are used for PCR-amplification (designed from the sequence NZ_JANCYZ010000002, genbank):

- Forward: 5'- GCTCTCTCGCAATCCGGTAATCC-3'
- Reverse: 5'- CATTCAAGTGTCAACTCCGTCGC-3'

Bands of the correct size are gel-purified and sent for sequencing. Positive transformants will be transformed with the plasmid pCP20 to remove the antibiotic resistance and/or the *sacB* gene.

pCP20 is a temperature-sensitive plasmid that encodes a temperature-inducible Flp recombinase. It is transformed into the cells by chemical transformation or electroporation. After transformation, immediately pour the suspension into 1-2 mL of LB medium (Luria Bertani broth contains L-lysine) and allow the cells to recover by incubating at 30°C for 1 hour. Spread the bacterial culture on LB plates with chloramphenicol and incubate overnight at 30°C. Pick 5-20 colonies, inoculate into LB (Luria Bertani) medium with 6% sucrose (w/v), and incubate overnight at 42-43°C.

Prepare 10^4 - 10^6 dilutions of the overnight culture and plate 50 μ L of the dilutions on LB plates. Incubate overnight at 30°C. Select randomly 5-20 colonies and patch on LB + chloramphenicol, LB + kanamycin, LB + ampicillin, and LB. Inoculate the colonies in 5 mL of LB medium. Incubate the plates and media at 37°C overnight. Select for colonies that are kanamycin, chloramphenicol, ampicillin sensitive, and that show growth on LB plates. PCR-verify the colonies to check for successful elimination of KanR and/or SacB by using the following primers:

- Forward: 5'- GCTCTCTCGCAATCCGGTAATCC-3'
- Reverse: 5'- CATTAGTGTCAACTCCGTCGC-3'

Bands of the correct size are gel-purified and sent for sequencing. The resulting strain should be L-Lysine auxotroph and capable of maintaining and replicating a plasmid harboring a minimal R6K γ origin of replication. If the plasmid further comprises a small transcription activating RNA (STAR) sequence under the control of a constitutive promoter, diaminopimelate decarboxylase should be produced, and the transformed strain should be able to grow in the absence of L-Lysine.

Plasmids' maintenance, replication, extraction, and purification

An engineered *Escherichia coli* strain obtained by following the instructions herein is called *E. coli* Δ lysA::[π -dttA^{ind}(lysA)] or *E. coli* Δ lysA::[parA-dttA^{ind}(lysA)]. π : the strain constitutively expresses π protein. parA: the strain constitutively expresses parA protein. dttA^{ind}(lysA): the gene that encodes Diaminopimelate decarboxylase is under the control of a small transcription activating RNAs (STAR)-inducible dual transcription-translation activator sequence. Examples of strains are *E. coli* Stb13[®] Δ lysA::[π -dttA^{ind}(lysA)] and *E. coli* DH10B Δ lysA::[parA-dttA^{ind}(lysA)].

The engineered strains are cultured on agar plates or in media containing and/or supplemented with L-lysine for their maintenance. Before transformation, cells are preferably rendered competent by following well-established protocols [49–52]. After their transformation with a given plasmid, cells can be cultured in 1-2 mL culture medium lacking or containing L-lysine at 30°C for 30 minutes to 1 hour to permit recovery. The culture can be spread on multiple minimal agar plates, such as M9 minimal agar plates without L-lysine and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 h to select for transformants. Positive colonies identified by colony-PCR can be cultured in minimal medium without L-lysine such as M9 minimal medium supplemented with glucose. 5-10 mL of culture medium can be used for standard molecular biology applications. Plasmids can be extracted and purified with commercially-available Miniprep kits by following the vendor's instructions.

The following plasmids are used for chemical transformation into engineered *E. coli* Stb13[®] Δ lysA::[π -dttA^{ind}(lysA)] strains: pR6K γ _eGFP, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_noPT, PP_R6K γ _eGFP, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_Tol2, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_ePB, PP_R6K γ _eGFP_SB, and pR6K γ _Tol2_mCherry. The following plasmids are used for chemical transformation into engineered *E. coli* Stb13[®] Δ lysA::[parA-dttA^{ind}(lysA)]: pcolE2-P9_eGFP, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_noPT, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_Tol2, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_ePB, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_SB, and pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry. The parental strain *E. coli* Stb13[®] is recommended

for the maintenance and replication of unstable plasmids containing direct repeats. Chemically transformed cells are added to 1.5 mL of Luria Bertani (LB) medium and incubated at 30°C for 1 h. The culture is spread on multiple M9 minimum agar plates supplemented with glucose and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 h. 5-20 colonies are screened by colony PCR and inoculated into 5 mL of M9 minimum media supplemented with glucose. Positive transformants are retained, and the culture media are incubated at 37°C for 12-16 h. Extract and purify DNA plasmids with commercially-available kits, such as Monarch® Plasmid Miniprep Kit by following the vendor's instructions.

Mammalian cells' transfection

Purified plasmids pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry and pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry are used for mammalian cells' transfection. The goal is to integrate the Tol2_mCherry cassette into the genome of the transfected cells. Total and fluorescing cells are counted at regular intervals to assess integrant stability and determine transfection and integration efficiency. $3 \cdot 10^5$ - $5 \cdot 10^6$ HT1080 cells are transfected with a combination of plasmid pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry and pCAGGS-mT2TP (a Tol2 transposase-expressing vector) or pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry and pCAGGS-mT2TP at 1-5 µg each, using FuGENE® 6 transfection reagent by following the vendor's instructions. Cells are cultured for 2 days, then trypsinized, counted, and sorted with a Fluorescence Activated Cell Sorting (FACS) system. Isolated fluorescing cells are further cultured for 2 days, trypsinized, counted, and FACS-sorted. This operation can be repeated during the next 6-10 days.

Expectation

Bacterial cells transformed with pR6Ky_eGFP, PP_R6Ky_eGFP_noPT, pcolE2-P9_eGFP, and PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_noPT will not yield any colonies harboring the plasmids after selection on M9 minimal agar plates lacking L-lysine. The absence of a STAR cassette, or the presence of sequence encoding STAR but without a promoter to drive its expression, renders the plasmids non-maintainable.

Bacterial cells transformed with PP_R6Ky_eGFP, PP_R6Ky_eGFP_Tol2, PP_R6Ky_eGFP_ePB, PP_R6Ky_eGFP_SB, pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_Tol2, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_ePB, PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_SB, and pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry will yield colonies harboring the respective plasmids after selection on M9 minimal agar plates lacking L-lysine.

The mCherry cassette of the plasmids pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry and pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry will be integrated into the genome of HT1080 cells. Tol2 transposases mediate the random genomic integration of the mCherry cassette, which is flanked by two minimal regions of Tol2 transposon that are necessary and sufficient for transposition [53,54].

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Conflict of interest statement

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Supplementary materials

Table S1: DNA sequences of important parts

Name	Description	Sequence
R6Ky_ori	R6Ky origin of replication	TGTCAGCCGTTAAGTGTTCTGTGTCACCTCAAATTGCTTTG AGAGGCTCTAAGGGCTTCTCAGTGCCTACATCCCTGGCTT GTTGTCCACAACCGTTAAACCTTAAAAGCTTTAAAAGCCTTA TATATTCTTTTTTTCTTATAAACTTAAAACCTTAGAGGCTA TTTAAGTTGCTGATTTATATTAATTTTATTGTTCAAACATGA GAGCTTAGTACGTGAAACATGAGAGCTTAGTACGTTAGCC ATGAGAGCTTAGTACGTTAGCCATGAGGGTTTAGTTCGTTA AACATGAGAGCTTAGTACGTTAAACATGAGAGCTTAGTAC GTGAAACATGAGAGCTTAGTACGTAC
colE2-P9_ori	Minimal ColE2 origin	GAGCGCCTCAGCGCGCCGTAGCGTCGATAAAAATTACGGG CTGGGGCGAAACTACCATCTGTTGAAAAGGTCCGTAAT GGGCTACAGAGCGATTTCGTCAGGGCTGGCCTGTATTCTCA CAATGGCTTGATGCCGTTATCCAGCGTGTGCAAATGTACAA CGCTTCGCTTCCCGTTCCGCTTCTCCGGCTGAATGTCGGGC TATTGGCAAGAGCATTGCGAAATATACACACAGGAAATTCT CACCAGAGGGATTTCCGCTGTACAGGCCGCTCGCGGTCCG AAGGGCGGAACTAAATCTAAGCGCGCAGCAGTTCCTACAT CAGCACGTTCCGCTGAAACCGTGGGAGGCATTAGGCATCAG TCGAGCGACGTACTACGAAAATTAATGTGACCCAGACC TCGAAAATGAGACCAGATAAGCCTTATCAGATAACAGCG CCCTTTTGGCGTCTTTTTGAGCA
Term_istr1	ISTR-1 terminator	CGAAACCTCGCTCCGGCGGGGTTTTTTGTTATCTGCA
Term_ BBa_B1005	BBa_B1005 terminator	CGCCGCAAACCCCGCTTCGGCGGGGTTTCGCCGC
Term_bidir	Bidirectional terminator	AAATATAATGACCCTCTTGATAACCCAAGAGGGCATTTTTT A
Term_T7	T7 terminator	CTAGCATAACCCCTTGGGGCCTCTAAACGGGTCTTGAGGG GTTTTTG
Term_T500	T500 terminator	CAAAGCCCGCCGAAAGGCGGGCTTTTTTTT
Term_1	Terminator	TCATGTTTGACAGCTTATCATCGAATTTCTGCCATTATCCG CTTATTATCACTTATTCAGGCGTAGCAACCAGGCGTTTAAG GGCACCAATAACTGCCTTAAAAAAA
Term_2	Terminator	GGCATCAAATAAAAACGAAAGGCTCAGTCGAAAGACTGGGC CTTTCGTTTTATCTGTTGTTGTGCGGTGAACGCTCTCCTGAG TAGGACAAATCCGCCGCCCTAGA
Tol2_5_prime	5' flanking region of Tol2 transposon	CAGAGGTGTAAGTACTTGAGTAATTTTACTTGATTACTGT ACTTAAGTATTATTTTTGGGGATTTTACTTTACTTGAGTAC AATTAATAATCAATACTTTTACTTTTACTTAATTACATTTTT TAGAAAAAAGTACTTTTTACTCCTTACAATTTTATTACA GTCAAAAAGTACTTATTTTTTGGAGATCACTT
Tol2_3_prime	3' flanking region of Tol2 transposon	TAATACTCAAGTACAATTTTAAATGGAGTACTTTTTACTTTTA CTCAAGTAAGATTCTAGCCAGATACTTTTACTTTTAAATTGAG TAAATTTTCCCTAAGTACTTGTACTTTCACTTGAGTAAAT TTTTGAGTACTTTTTACACCTCTG

SB_5_prime	5' flanking region of Sleeping Beauty transposon	CAGTTGAAGTCGGAAGTTTACATACACTTAAGTTGGAGCTA TAAAACCTCGTTTTTCAACTACTCCACAAAATTTCTTGTTAACA AACAAATAGTTTTGGCAAGTCAGTTAGGACATCTACTTTGTG CATGACACAAGTCATTTTTCCAACAATTGTTTACAGACAGAT TATTTCACTTATAATTCAGTGTATCACAAATCCAGTGGGTCA GAAGTTTACATACACTAAGT
SB_3_prime	3' flanking region of Sleeping Beauty transposon	ATTGAGTGTATGTAACTTCTGACCCACTGGGAATGTGATG AAAGAAATAAAAGCTGAAATGAATCATTCTCTACTATTA TTCTGATATTTACATTCTTAAAATAAAGTGGTGATCCTAAC TGACCTAAGACAGGGAATTTTTACTAGGATTAATGTCAGG AATTGTGAAAAAGTGAGTTTAAATGTATTTGGCTAAGGTGT ATGTAAACTTCCGACTTCAACTG
ePB_5_prime	5' flanking region of enhanced piggyback transposon	CGCAGCTAGATTAACCCTAGAAAAGATAGTCTGCGTAAAATT GACGCATGCATTCTTGAAATATTGCTCTCTTTCTAAATAG CGCGAATCCGCTCGCTGTGCATTTAGGACATCTCAGTCGCCG CTTGGAGCTCCCGTGAGGCGTGCTTGTCAATGCGGTAAGT GTCAGTATTTTTGAACTATAACAACCGCGTGAGTCAAATG ACGCATGATTATCTTTACGTGACTTTAAGATTTAACTCAT ACGATAATTATATTGTTATTTCTGTTCTACTTACGTGATAA CTTATTATATATATATTTTTCTTGTTATAGATATCCTT
ePB_3_prime	3' flanking region of enhanced piggyback transposon	CGATAAAAGTTTTGTTACTTTATAGAAGAAATTTTGAGTTTT TGTTTTTTTTAATAAATAAATAAACATAAAATAAATTGTTTG TTGAATTTATTATTAGTATGTAAGTGTAATATAATAAAACT TAATATCTATTCAAATTAATAAATAAACCTCGATATACAGAC CGATAAAACACATGCGTCAATTTTACGCATGATTATCTTTAA CGTACGTCACAATATGATTATCTTTCTAGGGTTAATCTAGCT GC
HA_left_lyxA	Left homologous arm from the 5' region of <i>E. coli</i> lysA gene	GCAGTATCTGGAGTTTGTATGCCACATTCAGTTCAGCA CCGATACCGATCTCACCGCCGAAAATCTGCTGCGTTT
HA_right_lyxA	Right homologous arm from the 3' region of <i>E. coli</i> lysA gene	ATTCGCCGTCGCCAGACCATCGAAGAATTACTGGCGCTGGA ATTGCTTAACTGCGGTTAGTCGCTGGTTGCATGATGAC
Pir_seq	Sequence encoding π protein	ATGCGCCTGAAAGTGATGATGGATGTGAACAAGAAGACCA AGATTCGCCATCGCAACGAACTGAACCATACCCTGGCGCAG CTGCCGTTACCGGCGAAACGCGTGATGTATATGGCGCTGG CACCGATTGATAGCAAAGAACCCTGGAACGCGGCCGCGT GTTTAAGATTCGCGCGGAAGATCTGGCAGCGCTGGCGAAG ATTACGCCGAGCCTGGCATATCGCCAGCTGAAAGAAGGCG GCAAGCTGCTGGGTGCGAGCAAGATTAGCCTGCGCGGCGA TGATATTATTGCGCTGGCGAAAGAAGTGAACCTGCCGTTTA CCGCGAAGAAGTCTCCGGAAGAAGTGGATCTGAACATTATT GAATGGATTGCGTATAGCCCGGATGAAGGCTATCTGAGCC TGAAATTTACCCGCAACATTGAACCGTATATCAGCAGCCTG ATTGGCAAGAAGAACAATTTACCACCCAGCTGCTGACCCG GAGCCTGCGCCTGAGCTCTCAGTATAGTAGCAGCCTGTATC AGCTGATTCGAAACACTACAGCAACTTTAAGAAGAAGAA CTACTTCATCATCAGCGTGGATGAGCTGAAAGAAGAAGT

		<p>ATTGCGTATACCTTTGACAAGGACGGCAACATTGAATATAA ATACCCGGATTTCCCGATCTTTAAACGCGATGTGCTGAACA AAGCGATTGCGGAAATTAAGAAGAAGACCGAAATTAGCTT TGTGGGCTTTACCGTGCATGAGAAAGAAGGCCGCAAGATT AGCAAAGTAAAATTTGAATTTGTGGTGGATGAGGACGAAT TCAGCGGCGATAAAGATGATGAAGCGTTCTTTATGAACCTG AGCGAAGCGGATGCGGGCTTCTGAAAGTGTGGATGAAA CCGTGCCGCCGAAGAAAGCGAAAGGCTAA</p>
parA_seq	Sequence encoding parA protein	<p>ATGAGCGCGGTGCTGCAGCGCTTTTCGCGAGAAGCTGCCGC ATAAACCGTATTGCACCAACGATTTTCGCGTATGGCGTGCGC ATTCTGCCGAAGAACATTGCGATTCTGGCGCGCTTTATTCA GCAGAACCAGCCGCATGCGCTGTATTGGCTGCCGTTTGATG TGGATCGCACCGGCGCGAGCATTGATTGGAGCGATCGCAA CTGCCCAGCACCGAACATTACCGTGAAGAATCCGCGCAAC GGCCATGCGCATCTGCTGTATGCGCTGGCGTTACCAGTTCCG CACCGCACCGGATGCGTCTGCGTCTGCATTACGCTATGCGG CAGCGATTGAACGCGCGCTGTGCGAGAACTGGGTGCGGA TGTGAACTATAGCGGCCTGATTTGCAAGAATCCGTGCCATC CGGAATGGCAGGAAGTGAATGGCGCGAAGAGCCGTATA CCCTGGATGAACTGGCGGATTATCTGGATCTGAGCGCGAG CGCGCGCCGTAGCGTGGATAAGAAGTATGGCTTAGGCCGC AACTATCATCTGTTTGAGAAAGTGCGCAAATGGGCGTATCG CGCGATTCCGAGGGCTGGCCGGTATTTAGCCAATGGCTG GATGCGGTGATTGAGCGCGTGGAAATGTATAACGCGAGCC TGCCGGTGGCGTTGAGCCAGCAGAATGCCGTGCAATTGG TAAGAGCATTGCGAAATATACCCATCGCAAATTTAGTCCGG AAGGCTTCAGCGCGGTGCAGGCAGCACGTGGTTCGTAAAG TGGTACCAAATCTAAACGCGCGGGTGGCCAGCAGCGCA CGTTCTTTAAAGCCATGGGAAGCACTCGGCATTAGCCGCGC GACCTATTATCGCAAAGTGAATGCGATCCGGATCTGGCGA AATAA</p>
lysA_seq	Sequence encoding <i>Escherichia coli</i> Diaminopimelate decarboxylase	<p>ATGCCGCATAGCCTGTTTAGCACCGATACCGATCTGACCGC GGAGAACCTGCTGCGCCTGCCAGCAGAATTTGGTTGTCCG GTGTGGGTGTATGATGCGCAGATTATTCGCCGCCAGATTGC GGCGCTGAAACAGTTTGTATGTGGTGCCTTTGCGCAGAAA GCGTGCAGCAACATTCATATTCTGCGCCTGATGCGCGAACA GGGCGTGAAGTGGATAGCGTGAGCCTGGGTGAAATTGA ACGCGCGCTGGCGGCGGGCTATAACCCACAGACCCATCCG GATGATATTGTGTTTACCGCGGATGTGATTGATCAGGCGAC CCTGGAACGCGTGAGCGAGCTGCAGATTCCGGTGAATGCA GGCAGCGTGGATATGCTGGATCAGCTGGGCCAGGTGAGCC CAGGTCATCGCGTGTGGTTACGTGTGAACCCAGGCTTTGGC CATGGCCATAGCCAGAAGACCAACACCGGCGGCGAGAACA GCAAACATGGCATTGTTGTATAACCGATCTGCCGGCGGCGCT GGATGTGATTGAGCGCCATCATCTGCAGCTGGTTGGCATT ATATGCATATTGGCAGCGCGTGGATTATGCGCATCTGGA ACAGGTGTGCGGCGGATGGTGCCTCAGGTGATTGAATTT GGCCAGGATCTGCAGGCGATTAGCGCGGGCGGCGGCTTAA</p>

		<p>GCGTTCCATATCAGCAGGGTGAAGAAGCGGTGGATACCGA ACATTATTATGGCCTGTGGAACGCGGCGCGAACAGATT GCGCGTCATTTGGGTCATCCGGTGAAGTGGAAATTGAACC GGGCCGCTTCTGGTGGCGCAGAGCGGCGTTCTTATTACCC AAGTTCGAGCGTGAAACAGATGGGCAGCCCATTTTCGT GCTGGTGGATGCGGGCTTTAACGATCTGATGCGCCCGGCG ATGTATGGCAGCTATCATCATATTAGCGCGCTGGCGGGCG ATGGCCGAGCTTAGAACATGCGCCAAGTGTGAAACCGT GGTGGCGGGCCCGCTGTGCGAATCTGGTGTGTGTTTACC CAGCAGGAAGGCGGCAACGTGGAACCCGCGCGCTGCCA GAAGTTAAAGCAGGGCATTATCTGGTGTGATGATACCG GCGCGTATGGCGCGAGCATGAGCAGCAACTATAACAGCCG CCCACTGCTGCCGGAAGTGCTGTTTGATAACGGCCAGGCAC GCTTAATTCGCCCGCCAGACCATTGAAGAAGTGTGGCG CTGGAAGTGTGTGA</p>
KanR_seq	Sequence encoding aminoglycoside phosphotransferase	<p>ATGAGCCATATTCAGCGCGAAACCAGCTGCAGCCGCCCGC GCCTGAAGTCTAATATGGATGCGGATCTGTATGGCTATAAA TGGGCGCGGATAACGTGGGCCAGAGCGGCGCGACCATTT ATCGCTTATATGGCAAACCGGATGCGCCGGAAGTGTCTG AAACATGGCAAAGGCAGCGTGGCGAACGATGTGACCGAT GAAATGGTGCCTGAAGTGGCTGACCGAATTTATGCCGCT GCCGACCATTAACATTTTCATTCGCACGCCGGATGATGCGT GGCTGCTGACCACCGGATTCCAGGTAAGACCGCATTTTCAG GTGCTGGAAGAATATCCGGATAGCGGCGAGAACATTGTGG ATGCGCTGGCGGTGTTTCTGCGCCGCTGCATAGCATTCCG GTGTGCAACTGCCGTTAACAGCGATCGCGTGTTCGCT GGCGCAGGCGCAGAGTCGTATGAACAACGGCCTGGTGGAT GCAAGCGATTTTCGATGATGAACGCAACGGCTGGCCGGTGG AACAGGTGTGGAAGGAAATGCATAAGCTGCTGCCGTTTCAG CCCGGATAGCGTGGTGACCATGGTGATTTTCAGCCTGGATA ACCTGATCTTCGATGAAGGCAAAGTATTGGCTGCATTGAT GTGGGCCGCGTGGCATTGCGGATCGCTATCAGGATCTGG CGATTCTGTGGAAGTGCCTGGGCGAATTTAGCCCCGAGCCTG CAGAAACGCCTGTTTCAGAAGTACGGCATTGACAATCCGG ACATGAACAAAGTGCAGTTTCATCTGATGCTGGATGAATTC TTTTAA</p>
SacB_seq	Sequence encoding <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> Levansucrase	<p>ATGAACATTAAGAAATTTGCGAAGCAGGCGACCGTGTGA CCTTTACCACCGCGCTGTTAGCAGGTGGCGCAACTCAGGCG TTTGCGAAAGAGACCAACCAGAAACCGTATAAAGAAACCT ATGGCATTAGCCATATTACCCGCCATGATATGCTGCAGATT CCGGAACAGCAGAAGAACGAGAAATATCAGGTGCCGGAA TTTGATAGCAGCACCATTAAGAACATTAGCAGCGCGAAAG GCCTGGATGTGTGGGATAGCTGGCCGCTGCAGAACGCAGA TGGCACCGTGGCGAACTATCATGGCTATCATATTGTGTTTG CGCTGGCGGGCGATCCGAAGAACGCGGATGATACCAGCAT TTATATGTTCTATCAGAAGGTGGGCGAAACCAGCATTGATA GCTGGAAGAACGCCGCGCGTGTAAAGATAGCGATAA ATTTGATGCGAACGATAGCATTCTGAAGGACCAGACCCAG</p>

GAATGGAGCGGCAGCGACCTTTACCAGCGATGGCAAGA
 TTCGCCTGTTCTATACCGATTTACAGCGCAAACATTATGGCA
 AACAGACCTGACCACCGCGCAGGTGAACGTGAGCGCGTC
 TGATAGCAGCCTGAACATTAACGGCGTGAAGATTATAAA
 TCGATCTTCGATGGCGATGGCAAGACCTATCAGAACGTGCA
 GCAGTTTATTGATGAGGGCAACTATAGCAGCGGGATAAC
 CATACCCTGCGGATCCGCATTATGTGGAAGATAAGGGCC
 ATAAATATCTGGTGTGTTGAAGCGAACACCGGCACCGAAGA
 TGGCTATCAGGGCGAGGAGAGCCTGTTTAAACAAAGCGTAT
 TATGGCAAATCTACCAGCTTCTCCGCCAGGAAAGCCAGAA
 ACTGCTGCAGAGCGATAAGAAACGCACCGCGGAACTGGCG
 AACGGCGCACTGGGCATGATTGAACTGAACGATGACTACA
 CCCTGAAGAAAGTGATGAAACCGCTGATTGCGAGCAACAC
 CGTGACCGATGAAATTGAACGCGCGAACGTGTTTAAAGATG
 AACGGCAAATGGTATCTGTTTACCGATAGCCGCGGCAGCA
 AGATGACCATTGATGGCATTACCAGCAACGATATTTATATG
 CTGGGCTATGTGAGCAACAGCCTGACCGGCCCGTATAAAC
 CGCTGAACAAGACCGGCCTGGTGTGAAGATGGATCTGGA
 TCCGAACGATGTGACCTTTACCTATAGCCATTTGCGGGTGC
 CGCAGGCCGAAGGGCAACAACGTGGTATTACCAGCTATAT
 GACCAACCGCGGCTTCTATGCGGATAAACAGAGCACCTTTG
 CGCCGAGCTTCTGCTGAACATTAAGGCAAGAAGACCAG
 CGTGGTGAAAGATAGCATTCTGGAACAGGGCCAGCTGACC
 GTGAACAAATGA

eGFP_seq_ec Sequence encoding an *E. coli* codon-optimized enhanced Green Fluorescent Protein

ATGGTGAGCAAAGGCGAAGAACTGTTTACCGCGTGGTGC
 CGATTCTGGTGGAACTGGATGGCGATGTGAACGGCCATAA
 ATTTAGCGTGAGCGGCGAAGGCGAAGGCGATGCGACCTAT
 GGCAAACCTGACCCTGAAATTTATTTGCACCACCGGCAAAC
 GCCGGTGCCGTGGCCGACCCTGGTACTACTTTAACCTATG
 GCGTGCAAGTCTTTAGCCGCTATCCGGATCATATGAAACAG
 CATGATTTCTTTAAATCTGCGATGCCGGAAGGCTATGTGCA
 GGAACGCACCATCTTCTTTAAAGATGACGGCAACTATAAGA
 CCCGCGCGGAAGTGAATTTGAAGGCGATACCCTGGTGAA
 CCGCATTGAACTGAAAGGCATTGACTTTAAAGAAGACGGC
 AACATTCTGGGCCATAAACTGGAATACAACAGCCA
 TAACGTGTATATTATGGCGGATAAGCAGAAGAACGGCATT
 AAAGTGAACCTCAAGATCCGCCATAACATTGAAGATGGCA
 GCGTGCAAGTGGCGGATCATTATCAGCAGAACACGCCGAT
 TGGCGATGGCCGGTGTGCTGCTGCCGATAACCATTATCTGA
 GCACCCAGAGCGCGCTGAGCAAAGATCCGAACGAGAAAC
 GCGATCATATGGTGTGCTGCTGGAATTTGTACCAGCGGGCGG
 CATTACCTTAGGCATGGATGAACTGTATAAATAA

mCherry_seq_hs 5'UTR + Kozak consensus sequence + *Homo sapiens* codon-optimized DsRed Fluorescent protein + 3'UTR

ATCGCTTCAGTCAAGATTTAATTAACGCCGCCACCATGGTG
 AGCAAGGGCGAGGAGGACAACATGGCCATCATCAAGGAG
 TTCATGAGGTTCAAGGTGCACATGGAGGGCAGCGTGAACG
 GCCACGAGTTTCGAGATCGAGGGAGAGGGAGAAGGAAGGC
 CCTACGAGGGCACCCAGACAGCCAAGTTGAAGGTGACCAA
 GGGCGGACCCTTGCCCTTCGCTGGGACATCCTTTCTCTC

		AGTTCATGTACGGCAGCAAGGCCTACGTGAAGCACCTGC CGACATCCCTGACTACCTGAAGCTGAGCTTCCCTGAGGGCT TCAAGTGGGAGAGGGTGATGAACTTCGAGGACGGCGGCG TGGTGACCGTGACACAGGATTCTAGCCTCAGGATGGCGA GTTTCATCTACAAGGTGAAGCTGAGAGGCACCACTTCCCTA GCGACGGCCCTGTGATGCAGAAGAAGACCATGGGCTGGG AGGCCAGCTCTGAGAGGATGTACCCTGAGGACGGAGCTCT GAAGGGCGAGATCAAGCAGAGGCTGAAGCTGAAGGACGG CGGCCACTACGACGCCGAGGTGAAGACCACATACAAGGCC AAGAAGCCCGTGCAGCTGCCCGGCGCCTACAACGTGAACA TCAAGCTGGACATCACCAGCCACAACGAGGACTACACCATC GTGGAGCAGTACGAGAGGGCCGAGGGCAGGCATAGCACA GGAGGAATGGACGAGCTGTACAAGTGATAAAGCCTCAATA AAGCTTGCCTCGACCAG
polyA_BGH	Bovine Growth Hormone Polyadenylation sequence	CTGTGCCTTCTAGTTGCCAGCCATCTGTTGTTTGCCCCTCCC CCGTGCCTTCCCTGACCCTGGAAGGTGCCACTCCCCTGTC CTTTCCTAATAAAATGAGGAAATTGCATCGCATTGTCTGAG TAGGTGTCATTCTATTCTGGGGGGTGGGGTGGGGCAGGAC AGCAAGGGGGAGGATTGGGAAGACAATAGCAGGCATGCT GGGATGCGGTGGGCTCTATGG
Prom_kanR	Promoter that drives KanR expression	AAAGCCACGTTGTGTCTCAAAATCTCTGATGTTACATTGCAC AAGATAAAAATATATCATCATGAACAATAAACTGTCTGCT TACATAAACAGTAATACAAGGGGTGTT
Prom_BBaj23108	Anderson promoter (BBaj23108)	CTGACAGCTAGCTCAGTCCTAGGTATAATGCTAGC
Prom_BBaj23105	Anderson promoter (BBaj23105)	TTTACGGCTAGCTCAGTCCTAGGTACTATGCTAGC
Prom_BBaj23104	Anderson promoter (BBaj23104)	TTGACAGCTAGCTCAGTCCTAGGTATTGTGCTAGC
Prom_1	Promoter	CACAGCTAACACCACGTCGTCCCTATCTGCTGCCCTAGGTCT ATGAGTGGTTGCTGGATAACTTTACGGGCATGCATAAGGCT CGTAGGCTATATTCAGGGAGACCACAACGGTTTCCCTCTAC AAATAATTTTGTTTAACTTT
Prom_CMV	Cytomegalovirus immediate early enhancer and promoter	TAGTTATTAATAGTAATCAATTACGGGGTCATTAGTTCATA GCCCATATATGGAGTTCCGCGTTACATAACTTACGGTAAAT GGCCCCCTGGCTGACCGCCCAACGACCCCCGCCATTGAC GTCAATAATGACGTATGTTCCCATAGTAACGCCAATAGGGA CTTCCATTGACGTCAATGGGTGGAGTATTTACGGTAAACT GCCCATTGGCAGTACATCAAGTGTATCATATGCCAAGTAC GCCCCCTATTGACGTCAATGACGGTAAATGGCCCCCTGGC ATTATGCCCAGTACATGACCTTATGGGACTTTTCTACTTGGC AGTACATCTACGTATTAGTCATCGCTATTACCATGGTGATGC GGTTTTGGCAGTACATCAATGGGCGTGGATAGCGGTTTGA CTCACGGGGATTTCCAAGTCTCCACCCATTGACGTCAATG GGAGTTTGTTTTGGCACCAAAATCAACGGGACTTTCCAAAA TGTCGTAACAACCTCCGCCCCATTGACGCAATGGGCGGTAG GCGTGACGGTGGGAGGTCTATATAAGCAGAGCTGGTTTA GTGAACCGTCAGATC

RBS_rhaS_20k	Native rhaS Ribosome Binding Site 20k	TATTCGCCGTGTTGACGACATCAGGAGGCCAGT
RBS_1	Ribosome binding site	GAAATAAGGAGGTAATACAA
RBS_BBa_K143021	Ribosome binding site	TACTAGAGAAAGGTGGTGAATACTAG
Rec_frt_wt	Flp recombinase binding site (wild-type)	GAAGTTCCTATTCTCTAGAAAGTATAGGAACTTC
Codon_stp_mf	Multiframe STOP codon	TTAGTTAGTTAG
LysA_HA_lft	lysA gene, left homology arm	GCATTATCTGGAGTTTGTATGCCACATTCCTGTTCCAGCACCGATAACCGATCTCACCGCCGAAAATCTGCTGCGTTT
LysA_HA_rgt	lysA gene, right homology arm	ATTCGCCGTCGCCAGACCATCGAAGAATTACTGGCGCTGGAATTGCTTTAACTGCGGTTAGTCGCTGGTTGCATGATGAC
Tta1_pT181	Dual transcription-translation activator vers.1 derived from pT181	TTGGGTGAGCGATTCCCTTAAACGAAATTGAGATTAAGGAGTCGATTTTTTATGTATAAAAAC
Tta2_pT181	Dual transcription-translation activator vers.2 derived from pT181	TTGGGTGAGCGATTCCCTTAAACGAAATTGAGATTAAGGAGTCGATTTTTT
Tta1_pT181_eng	Engineered dual transcription-translation activator vers.1	TTGGGTGAGCGATTCCCTTAAACGAAATTGAGATTAAGGAGTCGCTTTTTTTTTTATGTATAAAAAC
Tta2_pT181_eng	Engineered dual transcription-translation activator vers.2	TTGGGTGAGCGATTCCCTTAAACGAAATTGAGATTAAGGAGTCGCTTTTTTTTTT
STAR_1	Small transcription activating RNA (STAR)	AACAAAATAAAGCAATAAGGAATCGCTCACCCAAAGGATCT
MCS	Multiple cloning sites	ACGCGTCGCGAGGCCATATGGGTTAACCCATGGCCAAGCTTGCATGCCTGCAGGTCGACTCTAGAGGATCCCGGGTACCGAGCTCGAATTCGGATATCCTCGAGACTAGTGGGCCCGTTTAAACACATG

Table S2: Constructs' architecture

Construct name	Sequence architecture (5' -> 3')
pR6Ky_MCS	R6Ky_ori; MCS
PP_R6Ky_noPT_MCS	R6Ky_ori; STAR_1; MCS
PP_R6Ky_MCS	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBa_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; MCS
PP_R6Ky_Tol2_MCS	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBa_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; Tol2_5_prime; MCS; Tol2_3_prime
PP_R6Ky_ePB_MCS	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBa_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; ePB_5_prime; MCS; ePB_3_prime
PP_R6Ky_SB_MCS	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBa_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; SB_5_prime; MCS; SB_3_prime
eGFP_cassette	Prom_BBa_J23104; RBS_BBa_K143021; eGFP_seq_ec; Term_2

pR6Ky_eGFP	R6Ky_ori; eGFP_cassette
PP_R6Ky_eGFP_noPT	R6Ky_ori; STAR_1; eGFP_cassette
PP_R6Ky_eGFP	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; eGFP_cassette
PP_R6Ky_eGFP_Tol2	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; Tol2_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; Tol2_3_prime
PP_R6Ky_eGFP_ePB	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; ePB_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; ePB_3_prime
PP_R6Ky_eGFP_SB	R6Ky_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; SB_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; SB_3_prime
STAR_cassette	Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500
mCherry_cassette	Prom_CMV; mCherry_seq_hs; STAR_cassette; polyA_BGH
pR6Ky_Tol2_MCS	R6Ky_ori; Tol2_5_prime; MCS; Tol2_3_prime
pR6Ky_Tol2_mCherry	R6Ky_ori; Tol2_5_prime; mCherry_cassette; Tol2_3_prime
pcolE2-P9_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; MCS
PP_colE2-P9_noPT_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; STAR_1; MCS
PP_colE2-P9_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; MCS
PP_colE2-P9_Tol2_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; Tol2_5_prime; MCS; Tol2_3_prime
PP_colE2-P9_ePB_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; ePB_5_prime; MCS; ePB_3_prime
PP_colE2-P9_SB_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; SB_5_prime; MCS; SB_3_prime
eGFP_cassette	Prom_BBba_J23104; RBS_BBba_K143021; eGFP_seq_ec; Term_2
pcolE2-P9_eGFP	colE2-P9_ori; eGFP_cassette
PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_noPT	colE2-P9_ori; STAR_1; eGFP_cassette
PP_colE2-P9_eGFP	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; eGFP_cassette
PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_Tol2	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; Tol2_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; Tol2_3_prime
PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_ePB	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; ePB_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; ePB_3_prime
PP_colE2-P9_eGFP_SB	colE2-P9_ori; Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500; SB_5_prime; eGFP_cassette; SB_3_prime
STAR_cassette	Prom_BBba_J23105; STAR_1; Term_T500
mCherry_cassette	Prom_CMV; mCherry_seq_hs; STAR_cassette; polyA_BGH
pcolE2-P9_Tol2_MCS	colE2-P9_ori; Tol2_5_prime; MCS; Tol2_3_prime
pcolE2-P9_Tol2_mCherry	colE2-P9_ori; Tol2_5_prime; mCherry_cassette; Tol2_3_prime
parA_induc_lysA	HA_left_lysA; Term_BBba_B1005; Prom_1; RBS_1; parA_seq; Term_1; Prom_BBba_J23108; Tta2_pT181; lysA_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_T7; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; RBS_rhaS_20k; SacB_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; HA_right_lysA
pir_induc_lysA	HA_left_lysA; Term_BBba_B1005; Prom_1; RBS_1; Pir_seq; Term_1; Prom_BBba_J23108; Tta2_pT181; lysA_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_T7; Prom_kanR; KanR_seq; RBS_rhaS_20k; SacB_seq; Rec_frt_wt; Term_bidir; HA_right_lysA